

DEVELOPMENT OF A MANUFACTURING PROCESS FOR CONTINUOUS FIBRE-REINFORCED PRINTING FILAMENTS

Authors: Daniel Beermann, M. Sc., Dr.-Ing. Patrick Schiebel, Prof. Dr.-Ing. Axel S. Herrmann

Motivation FIONA project

- Additive manufacturing (AM) processes are establishing themselves as recognised processes.
- Due to a lack of process maturity, products are only used for components subject to low loads.
- AM with continuous fibre reinforcement offers the possibility of functionalising components.
- AM has the potential for a tool-less production of fibre-reinforced composite parts.
- The printing filaments are not available in sufficient quality or performance.
- Development of suitable continuous fibre-reinforced printing filaments is necessary.

FIONA project logo

Functionalised 3D printed structure
(© dpa / Carmen Jaspersen)

Goals and used materials

- Process development for the manufacturing of continuous fibre-reinforced printing filaments
- Utilisation of a high temperature thermoplastic as the appropriate polymer matrix
- Carbon fibre rovings are used for the continuous fibre reinforcement
- Target filament diameter: 1.0 mm with a fibre volume content (fvc) of 50 % - 60 %
 - Polymer matrix: high performance thermoplastic material (e. g. PPS, PEKK, PEEK)
 - Carbon fibre rovings: various types, aviation approved carbon fibre (6k → 12k)

Extrusion process

- An impregnation tool is used to manufacture the continuous fibre-reinforced filaments.
- Carbon fibre roving is preheated via fibre oven and heating tile (temperature: 250 °C).
- Thermoplastic material is extruded into the connected impregnation tooling.
- Meandering impregnation section in the tool, which is set to 400 °C to 380 °C (5 zones).

Experimental setup for manufacturing of continuous fibre-reinforced filaments (left) and impregnation tool (right)
(extruder: Teach Line® E 20 T x 25 D by COLLIN Lab & Pilot Solutions GmbH)

Process optimisation

- Increased distance between roving spool and tool for untwisting of the carbon fibre roving
- Spreading device to separate carbon filaments during preheating for easier impregnation
- Additional fibre oven to improve the preheating of the carbon fibre roving prior to tool inlet
- Cooling and postforming section after tool outlet to conserve round filament geometry
- Galettes for better control of the pull-off speed of the filament at high mould cavity pressures
- Larger filament spools (inner diameter = 305 mm) to bend filaments respectively fibres less

Sketch of the optimised experimental setup for the manufacturing of continuous fibre-reinforced filaments
(extruder positioned at a 90° angle behind the tool)

Results: Micrographs & SEM imaging

PEKK matrix + carbon fibre roving (12k)
melt pump = 4 rpm, pull-off speed 1,5 m/min
1,0 mm outlet nozzle, no spreading unit used

PEKK matrix + carbon fibre roving (12k)
melt pump = 4 rpm, pull-off speed 1,5 m/min
1,0 mm outlet nozzle, spreading unit used

Outlook further developments

- Manufacturing process adaptation and matching of fibre and matrix to develop a robust and process-stable 3D printing filament made of high-performance polymers (e. g. PEEK, PEKK, ...)
- Development of a modular tool to improve the individual carbon fibre impregnation
- Improve the cooling and postforming section in terms of target diameter and roundness
- Manufacturing process optimisation for the continuous fibre-reinforced printing filaments
- Evaluation of the filament manufacturing process

Optimised experimental setup for the manufacturing of continuous fibre-reinforced filaments
(spreading unit and postforming section not included)

- Innovative manufacturing methods for continuous fibre-reinforced 3D printing filaments were developed in the FIONA project.
- The process optimisations have significantly improved the impregnation and distribution of the individual filaments across the cross-section.

Conclusion

- The filaments produced show minor defects and edges in cross-section, which will be further optimised in the course of the project.
- The focus of further developments will be on redesigning the tool (impregnation) and optimising the cooling and postforming section (target diameter & roundness).

Funding (Funding period: 01/2021 - 12/2022)

The research project 3x3D-Druck was funded by the Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs and Climate Action (BMWK) within the framework of the Central Innovation Programme for SMEs (ZIM), for which we would like to express our gratitude. Funding reference number: KK5028301EB0

Funding (Funding period: 10/2020 - 12/2024)

The research project FIONA is funded by the German Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs and Climate Action (BMWK) within the national aviation research programme (LuFo VI-1), for which we are expressly grateful. Funding reference number: 20W1913D

